

A Study on Credit Risk Management in Arya Vysya Shree Rama Co-operative Society, Shimoga: A Case Study

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Abstract:

Credit risk is a major problem of banking sectors which has been facing various problems like lack of management skill of the workers and large administrative expenses are the major problems of cooperative banks in India. It can result in non-performing loans or risky investments, lower profit margins, decrease capital in the worst-case it lead to bank bankruptcy. Credit risk management, which includes the identification, measurement, aggregation, control and regular management of credit risk, has to be a critical banking activity. Credit risk is one of the major issues of every banks. To this research it was restricted to know how the co-operative society has handled the credit risk and to become familiar with the society's products and services and lending policies. Also this study examines how products and services have impacted to the society's performance and whether the society has been able to control risk.

Key Words: Risk Management, credit cooperatives, lending portfolio, credit risk

Literature Review:

The cooperative sector is a wide area in banking system and the study of each individual problem faced by these banks in terms of performance and operations is quite difficult. However, many studies are conducted to identify the causes for the failures of the cooperative banks in Urban and Rural areas. Below prepared table 1.0 contains the overview of major studies conducted in the cooperative sector. These research papers deliver the concept of credit risk and its impact on the bans financial performance.

1.Title: Risk Management and Efficiency of Works: A Study of Nepalese Cooperatives Societies.

Year of Publish: December 2021

Name of the Author: Gyanendra Prasad Paudel

Abstract: The people have created co-operative societies in order to achieve a common goals and objectives. It has provided poor, middle class and illiterate people in rural areas with access to capital market, while also becoming one of the most successful business models in urban

areas. The regulatory requirements imposed on banks by the central banks. A high level of risk has been seen in this sector. To study the information on risk management and productivity of work and using both primary and secondary data. The credit long term solvency risk and credit default risk ratios are 55% and 10% respectively and reflect the sensitivity or risk of such variable in the day-to-day operations of co-operatives to manage the risk.

2.Title: Review of Research on Credit Risk Management for Rural Credit Cooperatives

Year of Publish: March 2017

Name of the Authors: Xin Song, Li Li, Lei Xiao

Abstract: The problem of “Agricultural rural areas and farmer’s” have been effectively solved. The credit risk has been effectively regulated have all become key elements of our attention in the rural economic environment. The main classification and features of credit risk the model and evaluation of the credit risk.

3.Title: Credit Risk Management and Efficiency of Savings and Credit Cooperative Societies.

Year of Publish: November 2020

Name of the Authors: Josiah Aduda, Stephen Obondy

Abstract: This research will help to known the credit risk management and its contribution to growth in terms of improved savings, improved productivity, improved investment, increased employment, per capita income and credit to the private sector. The credit risk management was found to significantly performance in these studies. There is no specific evidence on the relationship between credit risk management and savings and Credit Cooperative Organization or Society.

4.Title: Effect of Credit Risk Management Practices on Lending Portfolio Among Savings and Credit Cooperatives in Kenya

Year of Publish: August 2013

Name of the Authors: Robert Mugo, Otuya Robert

Abstract: Credit Risk Management is a dynamic activity for savings & credit co-operative organization and society. Many investigations have been performed to determine the effects of credit risk management. The impacts of credit risk have been remained mystery to the savings

and credit co-operative organization or society management. Managing a lending portfolio is a good idea. The goal of this research was look in to the consequences of credit risk. Savings and credit co-operative organization society in country have several administration strategies. 59 savings and credit co-operative organization society were selected for risk analysis, risk evaluation, risk mitigation and risk analysis. In order to determine their impact on the lending portfolio.

5.Title: Credit Risk Management in Cooperative Sector Banks in India

Year of Publish: June 2014

Name of the Author: Supreet Kaur Gaba

Abstract: The establishment of co-operative banks was recognized in India about a century ago. The important component in the Indian financial system. The co-operative banks have assumed a primary and key position in the Indian landscape. The fact of that west and was developed by the west. This is due to India's unique social and economic structure, which is unlike anything else on the earth. These banks exist today by becoming major financiers for agriculture and associated business they have become a vital component of rural India as well as other industry.

6.Title: A Study to Examine the Credit Risk Management Process of District Central Cooperative Banks In Uttar Pradesh

Year of Publish: June 2018

Name of the Author: Nitin Saxena

Abstract: The purpose of this study is to assess the effectiveness of credit risk management system with the use of a questionnaire. The researcher used primary data from 19 selected DCCB. A total of 20 bankers from each of the 19 district central banks were approached by the researcher. Co-operative banks in the state of Uttar Pradesh and has visited 4 to 5 branches of each DCCB. The study discovered that credit risk management is successful management polices do not help banks increase their overall profitability or their market share price. To decrease in the bank's non-performing assets effective credit risk management.

7.Title: Risk Management in Cooperative Banks from the 21st Perspective.

Year of Publish: 2014

Name of the Authors: Adrian CONSTANTINESC, Mirela NICULAE

Abstract: International banking activity has increased as a result of the globalisation of markets, the extremely quick pace of technology, particularly in communications technology, and increasingly fierce competition between credit institutions to offer the most competitive products and services to customers. Since 2006, the cooperative banks have undergone major reforms as part of their reorganisation, which has resulted in the establishment of contemporary banking in this sector of the financial system with legislation that is in line with EU standards and has been tailored to the needs of the market economy. Only a comprehensive analysis and a thorough understanding of the most recent developments in banking financial risk management can offer cooperative banks in Romania effective management alternatives that will increase their profitability and liquidity levels.

8.Title: Effect of Credit Management on Firm Profitability: Evidence Savings and Credit Co-Operatives in Kenya

Year of Publish: 2015

Name of the Author: Samoei Richard Kipkoech

Abstract: This study's goal is to investigate how credit management (CM) affects a company's profitability. To determine the causal relationships between credit management and the firm's profitability, the study employed an explanatory research approach. Each and every Sacco in Uasin Gishu County was the focus of the investigation. Structured questionnaires were used in the study as the data gathering tools. The statistical programme for social sciences (SPSS), which offered descriptive and inferential statistics, was used to analyse and show the data.

9.Title: Empirical Analysis of the integration of environment Risk into Credit Risk Management Process European Banks.

Year of Publish: March 2008

Name of the Authors: Olaf Weber, Roland W. Scholz

Abstract: The credit risk management processes include environmental issues. It is analysed how environmental hazards are incorporated into all credit risk management processes, including rating, costing, pricing, monitoring, and work-out. Because only then can an acceptable risk management be guaranteed, it is crucial to incorporate environmental concerns into the entire credit risk management process. The findings demonstrate that banks only incorporate environmental concerns into the rating phase of the credit management process, even though this is advised given that these risks have an impact on all phases of the credit management process. Additionally, there are notable disparities in how banks who have signed the UNEP statement on the environment and sustainable development and banks that have not signed this integrate environmental risks.

10.Title: Environmental Credit Risk Management in Banks and Financial Service Institutions

Year of Publish: May 2012

Name of the Authors: Olaf Weber

Abstract: Analysis using a combination of methods of how environmental hazards are included into credit management. The qualitative and quantitative assessments recommend managing environmental hazards in credit management to minimise financial risks at all examined Canadian commercial banks, credit unions, and Export Development Canada. Even some of the organisations link sustainability and environmental challenges to their overarching business plans. All six of Canada's commercial banks, which account for more than 90% of the nation's assets, systematically evaluate environmental risks for credit, loans, and mortgages, making Canadian banks the best in their field when compared to those of other nations. We come to the conclusion that Canadian banks are proactive when it comes to loan environmental reviews and that financial institutions need to report on environmental risk management more closely tied to accounting.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Credit risk is a major problem of banking sectors has been facing various problems like lack of management skill of the workers and large administrative expenses are the major problems of cooperative banks in India. it can result in non-performing loans or risky investments, lower profit margins, decrease capital in the worst-case it lead to bank bankruptcy. Credit risk

management, which includes the identification, measurement, aggregation, control and regular management of credit risk has to be a critical banking activity.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Credit risk is one of the major issues of every bank. To this research how the co-operative society has handled the credit risk and to become familiar with the society's products and services and lending policies. Also examine how products and services have impacted to the society's performance and whether the society has been able to control risk.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To analyse the credit risk faced by the bank from each credit products and services of the cooperative society.
- To understand the concept of credit risk management in cooperative society.
- To assess the effect of risk analysis on credit co-operative society
- To examine risk management mitigation measures on credit cooperative.
- To study the techniques used to manage credit risk.
- To determine risk monitoring on lending portfolio of savings and credit co-operative.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data Collection method

1. Primary Method

Primary data is not collected for this study.

2. Secondary method

Secondary data is the data that has been already been collected based on the information.

The Secondary data for this study are:

- Journals
- Text books
- Websites
- Annual Statement of Arya Vysya Shree Rama Co-operative Society.
- Financial Records of Arya Vysya Shree Rama Co-operative Society

Sampling Design

Last 5 years financial data of the Arya Vysya Shree Rama Co-operative Society are used for this study i.e., 2018 to 2022

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1. Calculation of Standard Deviation for Deposit(In Rupees

Years	Deposits	Standard deviation
2018	102366896	39163004.5
2019	78950624	
2020	80573220	
2021	102366896	
2022	174899533	

Interpretation

From the above table and chart, we can prove that, when we compared the standard deviation value of above mentioned 5 years of deposits amount clearly shows that the value of Standard deviation 39163004.5 and it is comparatively less.

The High Standard Deviation tells values are spreads across the range. And the low Standard Deviation value tells that the values tend to be close to the mean of the set.

2. Calculation of Standard Deviation for Loans(In Rupees

Years	Loans	Standard deviation
2018	115824598	68681856.3
2019	10588049	
2020	108580422	
2021	115824598	
2022	204454998	

Interpretation

From the above table and chart, we can prove that, when we compared the standard deviation value of above mentioned 5 years of loan amount clearly shows that the value of Standard deviation is high.

The High Standard Deviation tells values are spreads across the range. And the low Standard Deviation value tells that the values tend to be close to the mean of the set.

3. Calculation of Correlation between Loans and Deposits(In Rupees

Years	Deposits	Loans	Correlation
2018	102366896	115824598	0.85
2019	78950624	10588049	0.86
2020	80573220	108580422	0.97
2021	102366896	115824598	0.98
2022	174899533	204454998	0.98

From the above table and chart, we can prove that, here the correlation of 2018 is the least and the 2022 has more value compared to other years. This shows that in 2022 there is high positive correlation which indicates both are moving in positive direction.

4. Calculation of Comparative Statement of different types of loans

Types of Loans	2021	2022	Changes in amount	Changes in Percentage
Vehicle Loan(2)	701228	901182	199954	128.514834
Building Loan	3508000	3871743	363743	110.3689567
Vehicle Loan (4)	1344079	1486417	142338	110.5900025
Business Loan	2102500	2161260	58760	102.7947681

Interpretation

From the above table and chart, we can prove that, while compared with above 4 mentioned loans, vehicle loan (2-wheeler) has a highest change in percentage of 128.51% and business loan has a least change percentage of 102.79% while compared to other loans.

5. Calculation of Comparative Statement of different types of deposit((In Rupees)

Types of deposit	2021	2022	Changes in amount	Changes in Percentage
General deposit	20051000	24217250	4166250	120.7782654
Fixed deposit	24203217	24304317	101100	100.4177131
Kalpavrksha deposit	86527300	96537257	10009957	111.5685535
Vasavi deposits	21561872	25617497	4055625	118.8092435
Kshyamaruddi deposits	753041	955041	202000	126.8245686

Interpretation

From the above table and chart, we can prove that, while compared with above 5 mentioned deposits, General deposit has a highest change in percentage of 126.82% and Kalpavrksha deposit has a least change percentage of 102.79% while compared to other deposits.

6. Calculation for Regression for Deposits (In Rupees)

Types of deposit	2021	2022
General deposit	20051000	24217250
Fixed deposit	24203217	24304317
Kalpavrksha deposit	86527300	96537257
Vasavi deposits	21561872	25617497
Kshyamaruddi deposits	753041	955041

SUMMARY OUTPUT	
<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.998771947
R Square	0.997545402
Adjusted R Square	0.996727202
Standard Error	1865332.883
Observations	5

Interpretation

From the above table and chart we can prove that, Here we got the regression value as 0.99, R square as 0.95, adjusted R square as 0.99, Standard Error as 1865332.883 and bserveation is 5.

7. Calculation of Anova for Deposits(In Rupees)

Types of deposit	2021	2022
General deposit	20051000	24217250
Fixed deposit	24203217	24304317
Kalpavrksha deposit	86527300	96537257
Vasavi deposits	21561872	25617497
Kshyamaruddi deposits	753041	955041

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	3435437042	1	3435437042	0.028885	0.869264888	5.317655072
Within Groups	95149103615	8	11893637951			
Total	95492647319	9				

Interpretation

The obtained value of F ratio of 0.028 with (1, 10) degrees of freedom. Go along 1 column and down 4 rows. The critical value of F is 0.02888. Obtained value of F-ratio is larger than this, and so conclude that obtained F-ratio is likely to occur by chance with a $p < .05$.

Findings

- It is observed that the total deposit position is increased from year to year continuously.
- It is observed that the total loans position is increased from year to year continuously.
- The overall performance of the bank is satisfactory. It has successfully improved its financial position. It is working in order to strengthen its financial viability

Suggestion

- The co-efficient of variation allows investors to understand how much risk, or volatility is taken in relation to the projected return on investments
- When you wish to predict a continues dependent variable from a set of independent factors. Regression analysis is a powerful statistical tool. It enables you to isolate and comprehend individual variable impact.

Model curvature and interactions, and make predictions. Controlling the effect of one or more independent factors while exploring the link between one independent variable and the dependent variables is possible with regression

Conclusion

- The main principle of co-operative society is Promotion of savings; self-help and mutual support.co-operative society and commercial organizations are different kinds feature.
- Bank should adopt modern banking technology for better customer service and developments of the bank.
- In cooperative society main aim is providing helps to farmers and rural development
- These are the sector established and control under the government. The policy, regulations and development project control under the central government or the state government.
- These are the sector which is regulated between the private and public sector.
- In a co-agent society capital is contributed by every one of the individuals.
- Society collected its fund on the basis of issuing the shares to the members and accepting the deposited from the members. The society collects surplus money from

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